

CONTAMINANT IDENTIFICATION IN WATER BY MICROBIAL BIOSENSORS – A REVIEW

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Abstract

The various micro-organisms are used to identify contaminated water. By the help of biosensors, drinking water pollution can be estimated. Rising environmental pollution is badly affecting water. Drinking contaminated water causes serious diseases in human beings as well as in animals. Microorganism in contaminated water can spread serious diseases. Biosensors are genetically modified to identify the occurrence of heavy metals, chemicals and toxins in contaminated water. Different microbes are used as biosensors such as *Escherichia coli*, *Algae*, *Fungi* and *Clostridium* etc. All these biosensors help to detect water pollution by different ways. For example, *algae* can detect water contamination by fluorescence during photosynthesis. Most rural areas are being affected by contaminated water. Most of the people living in rural areas are being affected by the polluted water as clean water is not available in these areas. People living in rural areas use water that looks clear but contains micro-pathogens that can cause dangerous diseases. Biosensors are important for identifying contamination, Due biosensor, can easily deduct pollution. Water is very important for the survival. Drinking contaminated water can cause serious illness. Therefore, clean water is very important.

Keywords: Microbial Biosensors; Water Pollution

Introduction

The biggest reason for water pollution and its scarcity is the growing human population and industrial pollution in the world (Khatri, Vairavamoorthy et al. 2008). Contaminated water kills millions worldwide (WHO, 2003). According to the report, youngsters under the age of five are most affected by contaminated water (UNICEF, 2006). About a decade ago, according to WHO research, most of the world's communities live in water-scarce countries, mostly in rural areas and less developed areas. The current situation is so bad that according to UNICEF, 1.7 billion individuals including those in rural areas will not have access to clean water. Some people live in rural areas that are still backward. There are no plants to treat polluted water in these areas. Such polluted water causes dangerous diseases. These include diseases that can be fatal. Due to water scarcity, people living in such areas turn to rivers, open ponds, springs and open wells for drinking water, according to WHO and UNICEF. Unfortunately, all the principles of cleanliness are ignored and these wells are often dug near toilets. Some of them are located near animal bathing areas (Maas, Perold et al. 2017). Due to poverty and lack of basic necessities, some people move to less developed areas where clean water is not available. Human health is not at all safe due to the use of contaminated water. Diseases caused by contaminated water are appeared not only by viruses, pathogenic protozoa and bacteria (Organization 1996), but also by some bio pesticides, hormones, phenolic acid, surface-active agent, toxins, metals and nitrates (Young, Wolfheim et al. 2012). The pathogenic micro-organisms present in contaminated water have a very bad effect on human health which is very harmful to human. Many pathogenic microorganisms present in contaminated water cause serious diseases which are diarrhea, cholera, typhoid, paratyphoid, hepatitis A, dermatitis, Intestinal fever, etc. (Butt and Ghaffar 2012). Biosensors are used to check water pollution, for the best measurement of pollution. Water is considered an intermediate risk, according to the WHO guideline for water pollution detection. Some bacteria like *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococci*, *clostridium per fringes*, *streptococcus facials*, *fungi* and *algae* are used as a biosensor for contaminated water. Among the living pollutants, E. coli is the prominent and its number varies between 10 and 100 colony forming unit CFU (Lindemann, Constantinidou et al. 1982). Contaminated water is also estimated from the presence of *Clostridium per fringes* spores, sometimes due to the flow of contaminated rainwater and drainage, which increases the number of coliforms in the aquatic environment, making water more polluted. Water tests are done to assess water contamination and various tests are done for this. If Streptococcus is not present in the water

then the water is not contaminated. Such water can be drunk(Warburton, McCormick et al. 1994).Sometimes the drinking water is clean in appearance but it smells bad. And when it is drunk, it has a bad taste. The water is contaminated with fungi that is very harmful for health(Hageskal, Lima et al. 2009).Water quality is degraded by algae that is major cause of water contamination and can be estimated easily.

Fig 1: There are many types of biosensors that are used for the contaminated water such as *Escherichia coli*, *Algae*, *Fungi* and *Clostridium perfringens*.

Escherichia coli is used as a biosensor of contaminated water

Escherichia coli is an indicator organism that plays a very important role in identifying water contamination(Krieg and Holt 1984).*Escherichia coli* indicates not only water pollution but also environmental and soil pollution etc. *Escherichia coli* is an organism that is anaerobic Gram-negative bacteria and also a negative rod-shaped germ. The *E.coli* is a stick shaped microorganism.

It can rely on any substrate with a large number. Its length is about 2 micrometers and *E.coli* diameter is 0.5µm. The diameter of *E.coli* with cell volume is about 0.6 to 0.7µm³(Odonkor and Ampofo 2013).Major reason for affecting the fecal range, the increase in *E. coli* population is mostly due to poor storage and lack of hygiene principles and storage conditions(Taj, Samreen et al. 2014). Fecal coliform is used less as an indicator of intestinal contamination than *E. coli* because intestinal contamination from *E. coli* is easily assessed. The same test that is commonly used for fecal coliforms is also used for *E. coli* from non-fecal thermo tolerant coliforms bacteria. Confirms gastrointestinal coliform, this test is designed to test for *E. coli* biology. We use this test to isolate *E. coli* from non-fecal thermo tolerant coliforms(Hussein, Abdullah et al. 2019). It is normally resides in lower intestines of humans and animals (Garrity 2007). Most *E. coli* strains are harmless, producing vitamin B12, K2, as well as expelling pathogenic bacteria from the intestine and preventing them from harming their hosts. But also certain *E.coli* causes dangerous diseases such as serotype O157:H7etc(Fotadar, Zaveloff et al. 2005). In fact, different schemes bring out the coliform by McConnell and bring out almost 128 types of coliform. Bergey and Deehan, in 1920 identified about 256.46 species of coliform(MacConkey 1909). For faecal contamination Indole formed the gelatin liquidation and production of sucrose yeast for differentiation coliform. These were the reactions of Pros core, the one of the most important tests to identify allergies(Hendricks 1978). All of these tests ended in IMViC (in dole, methyl).Water sanitary engines are used to identify contaminated water. But identifying contaminated water from the use of fecal bacteria is the fastest process. Despite their high numbers, these bacteria were considered less faecal and more common, including *Escherichia*, *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter* and *Klebsiella*. *E. coli* was produced by stress and the natural biological processes of *E. coli* develops some stressors that can be harmful and may cause an unpleasant change in its host animal and usually causes diarrhea which is dangerous for healthy children and adults (Nataro and Kaper 1998).There are also some viruses that cause serious illnesses such as O157: H7; and early deaths in young people and the elderly (Blankenhorn, Phillips et al. 1999) For the preparation of ethanol, carbon dioxide, lactate, and acetate, *E.coli* uses mixed acid fermentation during an anaerobic process. Mixed oxide fermentation is a process in which hydrogen GAS is produced by many pathways. These pathways are necessary to maintain the level of hydrogen. There are some bacteria that use these pathways such as Sulfate-reducing bacteria; this is what happens when *E. coli* live together. *E. coli* can grow easily at 37°C and this is the best temperature of the growth pattern of *E.coli*(Campanella, Cubadda

et al. 1997). In some laboratories, at 49°C temperature different strains can multiply. Its growth may be occurring in aerobic environment. But sometimes, it contains anaerobic breathing including redox pairs, oxidation of pyruvate acids, formic acids, hydrogen and amino acids (Ingledeew and Poole 1984). Stress is used to isolate *E. coli*. In sample different type of stresses are given to the different non-pathogenic *E. coli*. Due to stress on Pathogenic sample it delays. The small populations of *E. coli* grow on 44 and 45.5°C initially (Fotadar, Zaveloff et al. 2005). Sometimes acid and gas will not produce by pathogenic strains in 48th broths, because there is no any production from lactose in E, LST or BGLB, occur. If the media contains sodium lauryl sulfate then it will show growth at 44.5°C temperature and it can only possible when plasmid will remove. Pathogenic *E. coli* strains also contain some known to scramble that also contains many factors of virulence. According to the research, during selective enrichment cultures, 95% *E. coli* cells lost their plasmid (March and Ratnam 1986). *E. coli* should not be used for the detection of food or water isolation from the rocking strain. Other isolation of *E. coli* strain methods use for the hemorrhage EE that is insertion of O157:H7 that will be differently approached. H7 should be used in different ways instead of isolating hemorrhage EE through other *E. coli* methods (Kubitschek 1990). And many other *E. coli* that are present in K0157: H7 create strains that lead to biochemical differences that can be identified by isolation methods. O157:H7 *Escherichia coli* yeast either does not occur or is very slow, does not produce practical β -glucuronidase, but other tests are performed that give accurate results that include other *E. coli*. In addition, *E. coli* O157: H7 produces a stress that prevents rimonous agar plates from boiling. On the other hand, the non-sarbatol structure is associated with 60% of other *E. coli*, and most agar plates are evaluated by group's . Monoclonal antibodies, polymerase chain reaction and DNA testing and monoclonal antibodies such as Universe Pro Cider are used to differentiate organs from agar. (4E8C12) method that is specific to the outer membrane protein of E-coli O157: H7 and, therefore, both media on β -glu curonidase activity such as sorbitol MUG, which contains McKinsey, during sorbitol fermentation (Spano, Goffredo et al. 2003). The importance of cleanliness is due to the fact that is the number and identification of *Escherichia coli* depends on different estimates. Coliform and neural call is the definition of the ICOR group, due to the unique identification of *E. coli*, the specimens of IMVC (Leclercq, Wanegue et al. 2002). Red pH contains moderate methyl, acting as an indicator that indicates the ability of pigments to monitor glucose levels in high acids. Natural products such as butanadiol and glucose metabolism 2.3 acetane are both produced by IV, also

called the Vogues Proskauer reaction, if is used as a single carbon source if C represents Is, which refers to the ability of the bacterium. With the help of IMViC's profile which shows the exact ING due to recent data. It gives the same answer for E. Coli IMVIC as the Biotype I, II. And also gives the same result to samples II E. coli as a comparism of the some samples even in other more events. And it takes 48 hours for the partly explained the fact that detect and insole's large amounts. For this speculation additional tests are very important(Paton and Paton 1998).

Fig 2: There are five virotypes of *E.coli* that relays on the different hosts such as enter toxigenic and *enteropathogenic* relays on rabbits, humans dogs etc. On the other hand enter invasive and Entro-entrenteraggregative only relay on humans.

Algae is used as a biosensor for contaminated water

The measurements being taken to curb the spread of pollution in the world require the use of biosensors that can detect pollution. Such as herbicides due to pollution or Micro-algae that cause contamination of fresh water and seawater. But some biosensors, such as microalgae, help detect contamination. Types of micro-algae such as *chlorophyta*, *cyanobacteria*, and *Diatoms* help to

detect water contamination (Moreno-Garrido 2008). An important component of phytoplankton is also called green micro-algae such as chlorophyta. This is the type of algae that can easily survive in the system conditions that can be harmful for the other microorganisms. Algae are used in development of many biosensors, help to respond to important changes in the water system (Scognamiglio, Pezzotti et al. 2010). Due to the good stability for the production of biology signals, the green alga also known as *Chlorella vulgaris* is used for the creation of biosensors which help to analyse contaminated water (Védrine, Leclerc et al. 2003). With the help of chlorophyll fluorescence emitted by the activity of photosynthesis, can help in the detection of water that contains pesticides as well as heavy metals in water polluted (Durrieu, Tran-Minh et al. 2006). Algal biosensors were first used to estimate contaminated water based on photosynthesis. Such biosensors are used to detect contamination due to photosynthesis of living cells in water (Van der Heever and Grobbelaar 1998). Due to the change in electrical as well as optical signal, these sensors are based on the fluorescence of chlorophyll which is incorporated into chloroplasts (Naessens, Leclerc et al. 2000) while the amygdala photosynthesis with sensors follow the evolution of synthetic oxygen is done with the help of a Clark electrode (Dubinsky, Falkowski et al. 1987). Like *chlorophyta*, *Cyanophyta* that are also known as blue-green algae, are photosynthetic prokaryotic microorganisms, are also used as biosensors of contaminated water. Some inactivated cyanobacteria like *Synechococcus* and *Synechocystis* also work as biosensors to identify the toxicity of water. These types of blue-green algae detect the water pollution through their respiration, nitrogen fixation and photosynthesis system. *Diatomophyceae* or *Bacillariophyceae* are the type of the diatoms that also help to indicate the polluted water. They are belong to the eukaryotic micro-organisms and *Diatomo-phyceae* or *Bacillariophyceae* are most noticeable micro algae in the fresh water and oceans. All marine environments contain Diatoms (Reid, Tibby et al. 1995).

Fig 3: The chlorophyta (type of green algae) present on the filters that is indicated polluted water.

Fungi are used as a biosensor for contaminated water

Contamination with pathogenic microorganisms is a major concern for water consumers who are re-focusing on drinking water quality. Like other organisms, *fungi* play an important role in identifying water contamination (Hageskal, Lima et al. 2009). The fungus has never been so common in the past. The *fungus* was not considered as such, but later tests revealed that the *fungus*, like other micro-organisms, played a major role in testing water contamination. Different types of microbes in contaminated water cause serious diseases in humans. The fungus has never been so common in the past. The fungus was not considered as such, but later tests have shown that *fungi* like other microorganisms have played a key role in testing water pollution. Different types of germs in contaminated water cause serious diseases in humans. Water *fungi* were largely ignored, but modern research on contaminated water has led to a lot of work on the fungus over the past decade (SCHÜßLER, Schwarzott et al. 2001). When cases of fungus in drinking water came to light, water problems were examined in the 1960s and 1970s (Anglin, Hser et al. 1997), and it was estimated that the antinomy and *cyanobacteria* caused of tasteless and smelly water. The amount of micro *fungi* was also found in the water. According to 1980: study found that fungal infections in the water caused a variety of diseases (Rose, Martyny et al. 1998). Some Micro-organisms such as fungi and micro-bacteria are worked as detecting elements that help to convert biological response into electric signals. Biosensors that are Fungal-based more beneficial as compare to bacteria because fungal-based biosensors have ability of high binding capacity, fungal -base biosensors are more specific. Due to suitable properties, fungi make them self-more suitable applicant for preparing fungal-based biosensors (K Hussain, Malavia et al. 2020).

Normally fungal-based biosensors are specific for the electrical techniques, luminescence, growth rate fluorescence, colorimetric etc. In the field of molecular biology, recently fungal-based biosensors are used for the new coding insertion arrangements and also used in modification of fungal genome, offer more precise, accurate, and cost-effective procedures. And many other yeasts based on biosensors, are used for the identification of water pollution(Nugaeva, Gfeller et al. 2005).Some fungi are also causing infectious diseases that are harmful to humans.

Fig 4: *Acremonium*, *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Cladosporium* and *Tichoderm* all are the types of *fungi* that are found in the drinking water and are also used as biosensors of contaminated water.

Clostridium per fringes are used as a biosensors for contaminated water

Clostridium Perfringens are the type of biosensor that helps to detect water pollution. It is rod shape gram-positive bacteria. Its size is about 0.3-0.2 micrometers and its length is about 1.5-20.0 micromettes. *Clostridium perfengies* are the pathogenic bacteria that cause harmful diseases(Myers, Rasko et al. 2006). *Clostridium Perfringens* are associated with human wastes. However, it is not used in the U.S. and only in a peripheral area of Europe as fecal indicator systems. Another reason was the conflicting information that was developed according to preliminary research with this organism. An American activist who reviewed the 1945 searches and European workers examined

it in 1960 with bonds. According to most studies, the S.E. decided to compare the density of the pharynx with that of *Escherichia coli* (Bisson and Cabelli 1980). In the second absence, the results depend on the investigator and the sample examination, noting the presence of one of these indicators. Even at the place where the samples were taken. However, U.S investigator generally concluded that the presence of a *Clostridium perfringens* signaling system was of no value in indicating organ contamination *Perfringe* was found to be irregular in well and river water samples(Cabelli 1977).

The conclusions and findings are dependent on the investigator and the sample being examined. Even the location where the samples were taken were varied. American investigators concluded in general, that *C. Perfringens* indicator system did not have any value in indexing the presence of fecal contamination. Muhammad ET Morrison reported recently that *Clostridium perfringens* in water samples from wells and rivers was found to be irregular(Fujioka and Shizumura 1985).The results were compared with that of fecal *coliforms*, and concluded that these indicators were more accurate. Given the knowledge about ecology and physiology, it is not surprising that contradictory findings and conclusions have been drawn. Would expect *E.coli* in absence of *Clostridium perfringens* to be recovered from water subject to small-scale, immediate sources (Mueller-Spitz, Stewart et al. 2010). The *E.Coli* concentrations in feces, wastewater, and urine are approximately two orders to magnitude higher than *Clostridium perfringens*(Vierheilig, Frick et al. 2013). On the other hand, one might expect to isolate. It is not surprising to find contradictory results and conclusions, given the current knowledge regarding the ecology of the indicator systems. On the one hand, *E.coli* would be expected to be recovered in the absence(Bisson and Cabelli 1980). The conclusion and findings are dependent on the investigator and sample beings examined. Even the location where the samples were takes varied. However, American investigators concluded, in general that *Clostridium perifringes* in the water sample from wells and rivers were found to be irregular(Cabelli 1977). The results compared with that of fecal coliforms concluded that these indicators were more accurate(Chukwu, Nwaokorie et al. 2016).Given the knowledge about ecology and physiology, it is not surprising that contradictory findings and conclusions have been drawn. One would expect *E.coli* in absence of *Clostridium perfringens* to be recovered from water subject to small-scale, immediate sources.*Escherichia coli* concentrations in feces, wastewater, and urine are approximately two orders to magnitude higher than *Clostridium perfringen* (Labbe and Juneja 2002). On the other hand, one might expect to isolate. It is not surprising to find

contradictory results and conclusions, given the current knowledge regarding the ecology of the indicator systems (Vierheilig, Frick et al. 2013). On the one hand, *E.coli* would be expected to be recovered in the absence of *Clostridium-perfringens* when water is subject to small scale(Vierheilig, Frick et al. 2013). *Escherichia coli* densities in wastewater and feces about two instructions to size higher *Clostridium* can also be isolated without *E.coli* in cases of environmental stress such as prolonged transit in the water environment disinfection(Bisson and Cabelli 1980).

Conclusion

Many microorganisms in the environment cause pollution.They harm environment as well as humans.Several techniques are used to determine the pollution in the environmentbut modern researches shows that some microorganisms are used for detection of pollution in environment and it is a big achievement. *Algae*and *fungi* some bacteria like *cyanobacteria*, *clostridium* and some species of *Escherichia Coli* are used as a biosensor. These all species are used for detection of water contamination, food contamination and environmentalcontamination. *Algae*(blue green algae) and other strains show their functions by florescenceand by many advance techniques. It is mainly used for water purification.*Fungus*-based-biosensors work in luminoustechniques, electrical techniques and in colorimetry.It is used for water decontamination. *Clostridium perfringes* is a biosensor that is used for water contamination detection as an immediate source. Different advancements for progress of biosensors should be buildup for a healthy environment. It may save the lives of animals, humans and other worldwide organisms.

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